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Topic:

SIMULATING AND ANALYZING SIGNATURE-BASED NETWORK INTRUSION

DETECTION SYSTEMS USING MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES

BY

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DECLARATION

I, hereby declare that except for references to other people’s work, which I have duly acknowledged, this dissertation is the outcome of my research work, and that it has neither in part nor wholly been presented elsewhere for another degree.

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ABSTRACT

Security is essential for data sharing on the internet, as firewalls cannot detect fragmented packets and attackers alter their equipment and methods, leading to decreased productivity, financial loss, and brand harm. Weka Data Mining Software was used to create intrusion detection models, and the UNSW-NB15 intrusion detection dataset and attack categories included in Weka 3.9 were used to scan a network dataset for intrusions and classify them. The UNSW-NB15 dataset consists of 44 attributes and 9 different types of attacks.

To increase the speed of detection, some features are removed using Principal Components Analysis (PCA). The Machine Learning (ML) methods being examined include K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Random Forest (RF), Bayesian Network (BayesNet), and the Decision tree (J48). The experiments are run using the Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis (WEKA) tool with ten-fold cross-validation. The performance parameters employed are execution time, F-measure, recall, accuracy, and precision. In terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F-measure, J48 outperforms the other algorithms, with BayesNet producing the least accurate results.

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GLOSSARY

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
SIDS	Signature-based Intrusion Detection System
AIDS	Anomaly-based Intrusion Detection System
EIDS	Expert Intrusion Detection System
CIC	Canadian Institute for Cybersecurity
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DDoS	Distributed Denial-of-Service
DoS	Denial of Service
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HIDS	Host-based Intrusion Detection System
IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IP	Internet Protocol
IT	Information Technology
KNN	K-Nearest Neighbor
ML	Machine Learning
NN	Neural Network
NIDS	Network Intrusion Detection System
RAM	Random Access Memory
SIDS	Signature-based Intrusion Detection System
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
WEKA	Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis

OSSEC Open Source HIDS SEcurity

DEDICATION

This dissertation is a tribute to my mother, siblings, and all of my friends, whose love, support, and sacrifices made it possible for me to finish this work.

MAY THE LORD GRANT YOU ALL HIS BLESSING.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

As the Internet has grown in popularity, so have computers and their related crimes. With the implementation of digital commerce and banking via the Web, the implications have risen even higher. Many businesses would suffer catastrophic economic losses if the data on their computer systems were lost or stolen. The provision of security is therefore one of the most critical difficulties for many computers and networks, and several academics have offered various techniques to tackle this challenge, including firewalls, cryptography, and restricting network access. Kemmerer and Vigna (1999) wrote in their work the most serious flaw in all of these methods is that they are unable to identify network intrusions, attacks, or anomalies. It is therefore impossible to build a network without security vulnerabilities and malfunctions. Confidentiality, data integrity, and availability are three CIA concepts that summarize computer network security. Confidentiality entails only disclosing information per policy. Data integrity refers to the fact that information is not destroyed or corrupted and that the system functions properly. Availability denotes the availability of system services when they are required. External intruders are unauthorized users who attack a machine, and internal intruders have access to a system despite some restrictions.

With the rapid advancement of new information and communication technologies, computer networks play an increasingly important role in our daily lives. However, it is increasingly being used as a tool for criminal activity, resulting in significant losses for many businesses and countries. By discovering user behavior patterns from network traffic data, data mining and machine learning techniques have been widely used in network intrusion detection and prevention systems. Because traditional firewalls cannot provide complete security against intrusion, an

intrusion detection system (IDS) is required. Every business or establishment should have security equipment to protect their data. Kavitha and Suresh (2012) wrote that an Intrusion Detection System (IDS) is one such piece of security equipment that monitors and discovers intrusions or anomalous events in computers or computer networks. Hamdan et al. (2010) and Liao et al. (2013) defined Intrusion Detection System (IDS) as the process of detecting and counteracting malicious activity directed at computing devices and networking resources.

An IDS receives new sensor input, scrutinizes it, and then goes into action says Kavitha and Suresh (2012). Lina et al., (2013) also mentioned that an intrusion detection system detects breaches by inspecting a network or system and evaluating an audit stream taken from the network to look for evidence of despicable activities. Conventional security strategies such as identity verification, encryptions, and firewall rules are all situated in the first line of defense for the network security establishment. Each intrusion causes a series of anomalous behaviors in the system. The design of intrusion detection systems (IDS) was proposed as an alternative for network vulnerabilities.

Therefore, building reliable IDSs is critical in light of the global surge in cyberattacks. Any network anomaly detection system must have IDSs as a component. To ensure stable, high-quality, and uninterrupted services, network providers should tune and regularly monitor their hardware and software systems. Hence, this thesis work intends to create machine learning models that could provide predictive accuracies on intrusions or anomalies in networks. Machine learning (ML) techniques have gained widespread popularity in recent years and have been successfully applied to IDSs. These techniques can be used to develop effective signature-based IDSs that are capable of detecting known attacks with high accuracy. The ML models such as Random Forest, KNN, Bayes Net, and J48 algorithms can be utilized for this purpose. The purpose of this research is to simulate and analyze the performance of these ML models in signature-based network intrusion detection systems using the WEKA machine learning tool. Specifically, this research aims to

compare the performance of these algorithms in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and processing time. The results of this research will help to identify the most effective algorithm for developing signature-based IDSs and improve the overall security of networked systems. Several studies have been conducted on the use of ML in network intrusion detection systems, and they have shown promising results. For example, Alshammari et al. (2018) used Random Forest, Naïve Bayes, and Decision Tree algorithms to develop a signature-based IDS and reported an accuracy of 99.3%. Similarly, Hua et al. (2019) used a Deep Belief Network (DBN) model and achieved an accuracy of 99.58%. However, to the best of our knowledge, there is a lack of research that directly compares the performance of different ML models in signature-based IDSs using the WEKA machine learning tool. Certain performance evaluation metrics were specifically selected to evaluate the models been built. This research aims to fill this gap by providing a comprehensive analysis of the performance of different ML algorithms in signature-based network intrusion detection systems.

Overall, this research has significant implications for improving network security and contributing to the development of effective IDSs. The scope of the study will include the development of a simulated network environment, the collection of network traffic data, and the use of the Weka tool to train and test the machine learning algorithms. The performance of the algorithms will be evaluated using different evaluation metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

1.1. Background Studies

1.1.1. Overview of Intrusions and Intrusion Detections

Seth Webster et al. (1998) outlined that Intrusions are a type of computer attack, which is identified as any malevolent activities aimed at computer systems or the services being provided. Malware, physical injury, and service attacks are examples of cyberattacks. Since the emphasis of this study is on intrusions and intrusion detection, the words "intrusions" and "attacks" will be used

interchangeably to mean the same thing. Common ways by which an intruder can gain illegal entry into a system is packet sniffing, password guessing, social engineering, software bug, and system misconfiguration among others. The above categories are just meant to show the various attacks that a good IDS should be able to defend against. An Intrusion Detection System (IDS) scans network packets for possible fraudulent activity and notifies the administrator. The primary function is to detect anomalous activity and report it to the network administrator; notwithstanding, a few IDS programs will take a response governed by rules when inappropriate behavior is detected, such as obstructing certain traffic coming. Common intrusion detection systems in use today are Snort, SolarWinds Security Event Manager, Zeek, Security Onion, OSSEC, and Suricata among others outlined by Stephen Cooper (2022) in an article.

Therefore, building and analyzing ML models, their performances and the efficiency of IDS systems has been the subject of extensive research. Security experts see machine learning and artificial intelligence (AI) as potential technologies to help identify and combat cyberattacks as they become more complex. Machine learning techniques can provide an accurate, efficient, and automated solution to detecting intrusions in this situation. Of course, IDS cannot replace prevention-oriented strategies like authentication and access control, but it can be used as a supplement to discover the most initial potentially malicious accesses and inoculate the network from future attacks. Most IDSs operate instantaneously, but some do not and can only operate offline, that is, collect existing data and infuse it into their constructed heuristic. Simulation IDS can indeed be done in a variety of ways. For this, we employ a data-mining strategy. Data mining is one of the machine learning techniques. An expert IDS uses data-mining techniques to classify threats (EIDS). The stored records in an IDS database have many features with complex interrelationships that are difficult for humans to interpret. IDSs (particularly real-time IDSs) must use reduced selected features to pinpoint these correlations. For intrusion detection, there are two

approaches: misuse detection and anomaly detection. **Misuse detection** is based on knowledge of a system's weak points and known attack patterns. To detect each attack, we must first simulate the attack scenario. The main distinction between techniques is how they describe or model a perpetrator's behavioral patterns.

The anomalous detection approach assumes that each attack creates a deviation from the normal pattern. This approach has two implementation options: dynamic and static. **The dynamic anomalous detection method** examines audit data stored after previous network operations. We can recognize previous attacks on the system using data-mining techniques such as the decision tree. **The static anomalous detection method** assumes that the system under consideration has no variations. We assume that the hardware is constant while the software varies. The main disadvantage of an anomaly detection method is that well-known attacks may go undetected if they do not match a user profile. Another weakness is that the attacker can change his profile slightly and train the system to accept the intrusion as normal. The anomalous detection method can identify new or unknown attacks.

There are two kinds of intrusion detection systems: host-based and network-based. Host-based intrusion detection systems make decisions based on information obtained from the host. Network-based IDs collect data by monitoring network traffic between multiple hosts. Intrusions such as IP spoofing and port scanning can also take advantage of the TCP/IP protocol. Several machine learning paradigms, including decision trees, neural networks, linear genetic programming, support vector machines, Bayesian networks, multivariate adaptive regression splines, fuzzy inference systems, and others, have been used to develop IDSs in the literature.

1.2. Problem Statement

Security of computers and computer networks has become prevalent in most people's lives over the last two decades. Today, most computer security debates focus on the tools and tactics used to secure and defend networks. An intrusion detection system (IDS) should be able to detect and respond to all anomalous patterns and traffic within the system by monitoring, detecting, and responding to unauthorized actions. Singh et al., (2015) mentioned that an IDS has a complete data processing challenge with its large and imbalanced datasets. As a result, various strategies for dealing with this issue have been offered. Yet, the performance of ML algorithms used in these IDSs has not been thoroughly evaluated and compared in the last two years.

Moreover, Gurley Bace (2000) mentioned in a book that Network Intrusion Detection System (NIDS) alerts a system administrator whenever an intruder attempts to breach the network. Unfortunately, research and experience have shown that attackers can successfully circumvent almost any NIDS. Attackers can conceal an attack in two ways. First, they can alter how the attack is delivered, such as by dividing it into multiple network packets. Second, they can change the attack payload so that it no longer matches the NIDS signature, such as by using a different URL encoding. Unlike security protocol analysts, who use formal threat models to assess a protocol's resistance to attacks, NIDS analysts conduct their assessments using ad hoc methods and tools. Researchers presume that improving NIDS robustness necessitates the development of a formal threat model that exhaustively describes attackers' ability to evade NIDS. Because of the enormous quantities of security audit data as well as the complex and dynamic attributes of intrusion behavioral patterns, optimizing the accuracy of IDS has emerged as a significant open problem that is receiving research attention.

Again, Network intrusion detection systems (NIDS) are crucial in detecting and preventing cybersecurity attacks. Signature-based NIDS rely on known attack patterns to identify and classify

attacks, but they can be limited by the ability to detect new or unknown attacks. Machine learning models such as Random Forest, KNN, Bayes Net, and J48 algorithms have shown promise in improving the accuracy of NIDS. However, there is a need to analyze and simulate these models to determine their effectiveness in signature-based NIDS. Additionally, the use of the Weka machine learning tool can provide a standardized framework for comparing the performance of these models. Therefore, the problem statement is to evaluate the effectiveness of Random Forest, KNN, Bayes Net, and J48 algorithms in signature-based NIDS using the Weka machine learning tool and to analyze the performance of these models.

However, performance (in terms of the amount of time or space required) is frequently overlooked. The study enables administrators to understand system performance to make better decisions about how to choose the appropriate hardware or procedures for threat detection in various environments. Therefore, a thorough analysis of any system should be considered in maintaining the workability of such a system or machine.

1.3. Aim and Objectives of The Research

1.3.1. Aim

Overall, this research project aims to investigate the potential of using machine learning algorithm in signature-based NIDS and to evaluate their performance using Weka machine learning tools.

1.3.2. Objectives

- **To preprocess and prepare the network traffic data** and relevant ground truth labels for use in training and testing the machine learning models for signature-based NIDS.
- **To evaluate the performance** of the developed NIDS models using different **evaluation metrics**, such as true positive rate, false positive rate, accuracy, precision, and recall and

compare the results to identify which metrics provide the most accurate and reliable assessment of NIDS performance.

- **To simulate/develop and evaluate different machine learning algorithms/models** using the Weka machine learning tool including Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Bayesian Networks, and J48 decision trees, for their ability to accurately detect and classify network intrusion events.

Overall, the objectives of this research project are to evaluate the performance of different machine learning algorithms in signature-based NIDS, using the Weka machine learning tool, and to provide recommendations on the most effective algorithm and parameters for specific signature-based NIDS applications. By achieving these objectives, the project can inform the development of more accurate and efficient signature-based NIDS models for detecting and classifying network intrusion events.

1.4. Research Questions

This thesis primarily addresses the following queries regarding the examined signature/misuse detection strategies for intrusions:

- Which NIDS datasets were analyzed for the suggested solutions?
- How do different machine learning algorithms, such as Random Forest, KNN, Bayes Net, and J48, compare in terms of their accuracy and efficiency in detecting and classifying network intrusion events in signature-based NIDS?
- What is the impact of feature selection and extraction techniques on the performance of machine learning algorithms in signature-based NIDS?
- What potential drawbacks could each misuse detection method have?

- How can the results of this research be used to inform the development of new and more effective signature-based NIDS models?

1.5. Justification/Significance of The Study

The use of machine learning algorithms in signature-based Network Intrusion Detection Systems (NIDS) has become increasingly popular in recent years due to the advantages they offer over traditional signature-based NIDS models. Machine learning algorithms can learn from large datasets and detect novel attack patterns that traditional signature-based NIDS models may not be able to detect. The justification for conducting research on simulating and analyzing machine learning models like Random Forest, KNN, Bayes Net, and J48 algorithms using the WEKA machine learning tool in signature-based NIDS lies in the need to improve the accuracy and efficiency of NIDS in detecting and classifying network intrusion events. The use of machine learning algorithms has shown promising results in improving the accuracy and efficiency of NIDS. However, the choice of machine learning algorithm and its associated parameters can significantly affect the performance of the NIDS. Therefore, it is essential to compare the performance of different machine learning algorithms using different evaluation metrics to determine the best algorithm for detecting and classifying network intrusion events.

The performance of ML algorithms utilized in these IDSs has not been given a complete performance examination in the previous two years to give a current and up-to-date performance evaluation and performance comparison of ML methods. Also, ML models were built from the python programming language and others but very less in using this Weka Machine Learning workbench tool to build similar or better models.

The performance of these ML algorithms for IDS has emerged as an important open challenge that merits research attention due to the complexity and vast volumes of security audit data as well as the dynamism of intrusion behavioral patterns.

Also, the performance in terms of the amount of time or space required is frequently overlooked. Administrators will be better equipped to choose hardware or techniques for threat detection in varied situations because of this study's improved understanding of system performance.

- Advancements in machine learning tools: The WEKA machine learning tool provides a user-friendly and powerful platform for simulating and analyzing machine learning models for NIDS. It offers a range of algorithms and evaluation metrics, making it suitable for evaluating the performance of different machine learning models in NIDS.
- ML algorithms automate integrated data analysis workflow which provides detailed, convenient, and much more extensive insights into a wide assortment of these ML algorithms used in SIDS literature works (articles).
- This simulation and analysis process generates tables, and metrics that are simple enough for a layperson to fully comprehend and can be used in future research studies.
- An intrusion detection system (IDS) can be used to help analyze the number and types of attacks. This knowledge can be used by agencies to change their security systems or successfully implement controls.
- An intrusion detection system can also assist businesses in identifying bugs or issues with their underlying network layouts.
- As new data is fed into these algorithms, they learn and optimize their operations to enhance efficiency, continuing to develop 'intelligence' over time. New intelligence produced as a result is always a piece of new knowledge to an individual who seeks to dive into IDS problems and solutions using ML approaches.

Overall, the research on simulating and analyzing machine learning models using the WEKA machine learning tool in signature-based NIDS can provide valuable insights into the design and implementation of more accurate and efficient NIDS systems. The findings of this research can inform the development of new signature-based NIDS models that can effectively detect and classify network intrusion events, thus improving network security.

1.6. Scope Of the Study

This research work was mainly done on Signature-Based Intrusion Detection Systems (SIDS). The work trains and creates models for intrusion detection predictive problems. The scope of the study on simulating and analyzing machine learning models like Random Forest, KNN, Bayes Net, and J48 algorithms making use of the WEKA machine learning tool in signature-based network intrusion detection systems includes:

- 1. Data collection and Preprocessing:** The study will involve the collection of network traffic data from the UNSW-NB15 dataset, which will be used for training and testing the machine learning models. The collected data will be preprocessed to remove irrelevant data, convert categorical data to numerical data, and normalize the data for machine learning algorithms.
- 2. Model development:** The study will involve the development of machine learning models using Random Forest, KNN, Bayes Net, and J48 algorithms for signature-based NIDS. The models will be trained on the preprocessed dataset and evaluated using the WEKA machine learning tool.
- 3. Performance evaluation:** The study will evaluate the performance of the developed models using different evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and area under the curve (AUC) to determine the best-performing model.

4. **Comparison of models:** The study will compare the performance of the developed models and identify the strengths and weaknesses of each model.

5. **Experiment design and implementation:** The study will involve designing and implementing experiments to evaluate the performance of machine learning algorithms using the WEKA machine learning tool. The experiments will involve varying parameters such as the number of trees in the Random Forest algorithm or the number of neighbors in the KNN algorithm to determine their impact on the performance of the algorithms.

6. **Analysis of results:** The study will analyze the results of the performance evaluation and provide insights into the effectiveness of the developed models for signature-based NIDS.

The scope of the study is limited to the use of machine learning models for signature-based NIDS and does not include other types of NIDS such as anomaly-based or hybrid NIDS. The UNSW-NB15 intrusion detection dataset used was analyzed and attack anomalies were found. The work was then concluded and some recommendations were stated for future works. The study will also focus on using the WEKA machine learning tool for simulation and analysis, and other machine learning tools may not be included in the scope of the study.

1.7. Outline Of Methodology

The study makes use of the design science research method with an experimental approach. The study made use of the Weka software program to build and analyze the machine learning models and evaluate their performances in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and f-measure.

The methodology includes the following steps:

1. **Data collection and pre-processing:** Collect network traffic data from different sources and pre-process the data to ensure its suitability for machine learning algorithms. The UNSW-NB15 dataset will be used for training and testing machine learning models.
2. **Feature selection:** Select relevant features from the network traffic data for training the machine learning models. This will involve using techniques such as correlation analysis and principal component analysis.
3. **Experiment design and implementation:** Design and implement experiments to evaluate the performance of machine learning algorithms using the WEKA machine learning tool. The experiments will involve varying parameters such as the number of trees in the Random Forest algorithm or the number of neighbors in the KNN algorithm to determine their impact on the performance of the algorithms.
4. **Model training and testing:** Train the machine learning models using the selected features and evaluate their performance using different evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, ROC curve, and AUC.
5. **Performance analysis:** Analyze the performance of different machine learning models using the evaluation metrics to identify the strengths and weaknesses of each machine learning algorithm and determine which algorithms are most suitable for use in signature-based NIDS.
6. **Comparison with existing NIDS:** Compare the performance of machine learning models with existing signature-based NIDS to determine their effectiveness in detecting network intrusions.
7. **Optimization:** Optimize the machine learning models to improve their performance by fine-tuning the parameters or using different feature selection techniques.

8. **Discussion and conclusion:** Discuss the findings of the study and draw conclusions on the effectiveness of machine learning models in signature-based NIDS.

Overall, the methodology for simulating and analyzing machine learning models using the WEKA machine learning tool in signature-based network intrusion detection systems will involve collecting and pre-processing data, selecting relevant features, designing and implementing experiments, training and testing machine learning models, analyzing performance, optimizing the models, and drawing conclusions.

1.8. Contributions

The research had the following major contributions:

1. **Comparative evaluation of machine learning algorithms:** The research will evaluate the performance of different machine learning algorithms in signature-based NIDS using various evaluation metrics. This will provide a comparative analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of each algorithm, which can guide the selection of the most suitable algorithm for a specific application. A comprehensive work among different authors that targeted performance evaluation and comparison of ML approaches was observed. Analysis and evaluations were carried out on the Machine Learning techniques used across the collected papers on Signature-based Intrusions. Exploration of the comparative study of various ML algorithms used in IDS for several applications like big data, 5G networks, smart cities, and the Internet of Things on Signature-based Intrusion Detection Systems.

2. **Optimization of machine learning models:** The research will explore different techniques to optimize machine learning models and improve their performance. This will include fine-tuning

the parameters and feature selection techniques, which can lead to more accurate and efficient detection of network intrusions.

3. Insights into the performance of signature-based NIDS: The research will provide insights into the performance of signature-based NIDS, including their ability to detect network intrusions and their limitations. This can guide the development of more effective intrusion detection systems in the future. The performance metrics of the Machine Learning techniques were also implemented.

4. Validation of WEKA tool in NIDS: The research will validate the use of the WEKA machine learning tool for developing and evaluating machine learning models in signature-based NIDS. This can help establish the effectiveness of the WEKA tool in the NIDS domain and encourage its wider adoption. Implementation of the Weka Software Program for evaluating ML techniques was then handled.

5. Providing the screenshots guideline, graphs, and tables with vivid explanations.

6. Comparing & contrasting the implementation results.

Overall, the research on simulating and analyzing machine learning models using the WEKA machine learning tool in signature-based network intrusion detection systems is expected to contribute to the advancement of intrusion detection systems, guide the selection of suitable machine learning algorithms for specific applications, and validate the use of the WEKA tool in the NIDS domain.

1.9. Organization Of Thesis Chapters

This thesis will comprise five chapters that are going to describe the studies which have been carried out.

- The first chapter (Chapter 1) includes an introduction and discourse on the study's background. This chapter would also include the research problem, objectives, methodology outline, justification for the study, and organization of chapters.
- The second chapter (Chapter 2) includes an analysis of relevant literature on several studies that have been conducted on this topic. The methods and technologies used are also discussed in the literature review.
- The third chapter (Chapter 3) makes up the methodology. The methodology includes a detailed discussion of data acquisition, data information, tools used, and the various algorithms to be used. It has an in-depth description of the tools, and repositories (datasets).
- The fourth chapter (Chapter 4) also covers the study's rollout, desired outcome, and discussions. It also includes the model implementation and an analysis of the evaluation results. The metrics used to evaluate the models and the study's findings would also be discussed.
- Finally, the last chapter (Chapter 5) brings the research to a close. This chapter would contain suggestions and future works.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Introduction

This chapter covers relevant work on intrusion detection methodologies such as anomaly attack detection, abuse detection systems, hybrid intrusion detection, machine learning, and deep learning algorithms, how intrusion detection systems evolved, which integrates some or all of these approaches, and vulnerability scanning infrastructures to solve issues in Intrusion detection systems based on signatures (SIDS). A review of

2.2. Theoretical Works

2.2.1. Intrusion Detection Systems: History and Advancement

In the beginning, Kemmerer and Vigna (2002) outlined in a magazine that intrusion detection was done by system administrators who sat in front of a computer and monitored user activities. When a rarely used printer becomes unusually active or a user who is supposed to be on vacation logs in locally, the system administrator suspects an intrusion. This early way of system administrators detecting intrusions was not scalable, despite its effectiveness at the time. In the next phase of the intrusion detection techniques, system administrators scrutinized the audit logs for proof or evidence of hostile or anomalous activity. System administrators used to create audit logs on fan-folded papers that piled up four to five feet high at the end of the week in the late 1970s and early 1980s. It took time for the system administrators to pore through the stack of printed fan-folded sheets for signs of intrusions. Audit logs were largely used as a tool for forensics to discover the cause of a security issue by administrators because there was such a large volume of data and analysis was done manually. As a result, attacks were difficult to identify and halt. As storage space became less expensive, audit logs were moved online, and academics developed tools to analyze the data contained in the audit logs. Because data analysis is computation-heavy and time-

consuming, the intrusion detection programs were written to run while the system's user load was low, allowing intrusions to be identified after they occurred. Still, this approach was not feasible enough, and thus the need for a different intrusion detection method.

Furthermore, the US Air Force which was one of the major utilizers of computers at the time became increasingly aware of these computer security flaws. A report documented by James Anderson (1972) outlined the fact that the US Air Force was faced with the tough challenge of enabling shared access to its computer systems. As a result, there was a serious issue that persists to this day. The question now remains: how can different classification domains on the same network be secured? In another phase, Denning and Neumann (1984-1986) developed an Expert System to Detect Intrusions (IDES) which came initially as an expert system that was rule-based and was trained to locate known harmful behaviors. This very approach has since been modified and improved over time to become the Next-Generation Intrusion detection expert system (NIDES). Anderson (1980s - 1990s) also worked on many pieces of research that largely talk about this intrusion-detection expert system (IDES). And much of those works on IDES were largely supported by the US government at the time. Projects such as Discovery, Multics Intrusion Detection and Alerting System (MIDAS), Haystack, Intrusion Reporter (NADIR), and Network Audit Director were created to identify and handle intrusions.

In the 1990s, Todd Heberlein of UC Davis was the first to introduce the concept of network intrusion detection. Heberlein (1990) was the creator and main author of the first network intrusion identification system called Network Security Monitor (NSM) which was published. The network traffic was studied using NSM and gave enormous amounts of data at key government locations. This increased awareness generated a surge in interest in the field of intrusion detection, resulting in a surge in investment in that industry. Heberlein also participated in the DIDS project, where he and the Haystack team co-invented the notion of hybrid intrusion detection. The efforts of the

Haystack project, as well as the launching of the Network Security Monitor, changed and monetized the IDS sector. Haystack Laboratories was the very first commercial IDS firm, and it made a name for itself with its Stalker series of host-based products. SAIC was also developing the Computer Crimes Detection System, a host-based intrusion detection system (CMDS). Similarly, the Air Force's Evolution of Intrusion Detection Devices Intelligence Analysis Service Center developed the Automated Security Metric System (ASIM) to monitor network traffic on the US Air Force's systems. ASIM made great progress in overcoming the scalability and portability concerns that hampered NID solutions earlier. Furthermore, ASIM was the first intrusion detection system for networks that have both hardware devices and software components. The Emergency Computer Response Team of the Air Force (AFCERT) still uses and manages ASIM at several locations around the world.

Recently in the past few years, IDS is currently among the top-selling security vendor technologies, according to Globe Newswire (2022) industry figures, and this trend should continue. ISS offers a hybrid intrusion detection solution as well as a standalone NID system. With the release of RealSecure, ISS entered the NID market, almost simultaneously with the acquisition of NetRanger by CISCO. They added a host-based component two years later, completing their hybrid IDS offering. With the acquisition of Network ICE and its highly regarded NID products, including their new gigabit NID system, ISS has made yet another stride toward the dominance of the IDS industry. IDS advancements will eventually propel cybersecurity into an entirely new realm of automated security intelligence. IDS is also being accelerated by government schemes such as the Federal Intrusion Detection Network (FIDNet), formed under the President's Decision Directive 63. After a year, Cisco realized the value of network attack detection and purchased the Wheel Group to provide security solutions. Eventually, researchers were able to create real-time intrusion detection systems for examining audit data earlier in the 1990s. These technologies

developed by Kemmerer and Vigna (2002) for the identification of intrusions were possible for handling attacks and allowing for real-time reactions to such intrusions.

To summarize, Anderson, Heberlein, and Denning's work gave birth to the IDS notion. Government financing and corporate interest aided in the development of their notion into a practical solution that finally made it into the mainstream of network security. Intrusion detection has gone a long way, and it is now a vital tool for identifying, monitoring, and responding to security threats. IDS technology has had multiple revisions and owners as it progressed from concept to implementation and finally to commercially feasible tools. Nevertheless, identifying intrusions has become ubiquitous as a means of preventing exploitation. Additionally, many intrusion identification systems, both commercial and freeware, have been developed in recent decades to handle system intrusions. Modern strategies are being employed to improve the success rate of such programs. Intrusion Detecting Systems (IDS) can now be automated using machine learning techniques or deep learning techniques to handle large datasets. Local anomaly detection algorithms have also been refined to the point that they can now detect intrusions with higher accuracies. All these gave birth to the idea of artificial intelligence.

So, what comes next? App intrusion detection, heuristics, rules-based intrusion detection, artificial intelligence integration, and who knows what else. Whatever the future holds for intrusion detection technology, one thing is certain: it is already an essential element of data security. Thus, there is a need to implement better methods in the design and manufacturing of these detection systems using Artificial Intelligence-related algorithms.

2.2.2. Intrusion Detection System (Ids)

A hardware or software application that monitors a network system for malicious activity or policy breaches can be referred to as an intrusion detection system (IDS). Any intrusion activity or violation is usually notified to an administrator or a centralized security event management system. The house's lock system, for example, protects it from theft. However, if someone tries entry into the house by breaking the door lock, the burglar alarm detects that the lock has been damaged or tampered with and sounds an alarm to inform the owner.

Furthermore, firewalls are particularly good for monitoring inbound internet traffic to avoid the firewall. External users, for example, can dial into the Intranet using a modem deployed in the company's private network; the firewall will not notice this type of access. Again, intrusion detection is the never-ending active attempt to detect or discover the existence of intruding activities. When it comes to computers and network infrastructure, intrusion detection (ID) has a far wider perspective. It encompasses all methods for detecting unauthorized network or computing device usage. This is accomplished using an application developed with the primary aim of discovering unexpected or aberrant behaviors. IDS has a very close counterpart that they sometimes move together, and that is the intrusion prevention system. They can work separately or in conjunction with IDS.

2.2.3. Intrusion Prevention System (IPS)

Intrusion Prevention System (IPS) is another network technology for preventing security threats that examines network communication flows to identify and halt vulnerability attacks. It sometimes works in conjunction with the IDS to identify and stop intrusions at the same time.

Prevention systems are also grouped as Network (NIPS) and Host (HIPS). These systems watch the network traffic and automatically take actions to protect networks and systems.

2.2.4. Classifications of Intrusion Detecting Systems

i. Host-Based Intrusion Detecting Systems (HIDS)

The HIDS monitors the state of systems on separate hosts or devices. HIDS can monitor file access, file permission changes, and which programs have access to which resources. An alert is delivered to the administrator of the system files that have been updated or destroyed.

ii. Network-Based Intrusion Detection Systems (NIDS)

The NIDS is placed properly throughout the network for traffic monitoring. According to Tiwari (2017), an intrusion-detecting system for networks (NIDS) is installed along a LAN line. They analyze traffic across the entire subnet and check it against a database of known assaults. An alarm is set off and forwarded to the security administrator after an attack is detected or abnormal behavior is detected.

iii. Hybrid Intrusion Detecting Systems

Hybrid attack detecting systems are a type of detection system that uses a combination of technologies. Data from various sensors are combined. Both host and network-based intrusion-detecting systems are frequently combined into a single central analyzer that can better react to intrusion events.

2.2.5. Intrusion Detecting Methods

There are two ways in which IDS uses to detect and respond to attacks on a network or a computer, that is the signature-based IDS and the anomaly-based IDS.

2.2.5.1. Signature-based Intrusion Detection (SIDS)

SIDS uses a table of harmful signatures to define attacks. Khraisat et al., (2019) referred to them as Knowledge-based Detecting or Abuse Detecting Systems. Thousands of businesses rely on such systems since they are simple to comprehend and utilize. A signal is set off in the SIDS when an attack pattern matches the pattern of a past intrusion existing in the data repository. SIDS is used in a variety of popular tools, including Snort by Roesch (1999) and NetSTAT by Vigna & Kemmerer (1999). Traditional SIDS approaches struggle to recognize assaults that span many packets. SIDS, on the other hand, cannot capture zero-day intrusions since the database lacks a matching signature until the latest attack's signature is extracted and saved.

2.2.5.2. Anomaly-based Intrusion Detecting System (AIDS)

Because of its ability to transcend the limitations of SIDS, AIDS has attracted a large number of academics. A normal model of a computer system's behavior is developed using machine learning, statistical-based, or knowledge-based methods in AIDS. Any major difference between observed behavior and model behavior is considered an anomaly, which might be construed as an intrusion. Alazab et al., (2012) outlined the key benefit of AIDS is its ability to detect zero-day attacks because it does depend on patterns stored in a database to detect aberrant user activity. When the investigated behavior deviates from usual behavior, AIDS sends out a warning signal. When AIDS first detects internal harmful activity, it raises an alarm if an intruder begins making transactions in a stolen account that are not identifiable in normal user activity. Second, because the system is built from personalized profiles, it is difficult for a cybercriminal to recognize what is regular user activity without triggering an alert.

The key distinction between SIDS and AIDS is that AIDS can recognize zero-day assaults, but SIDS only recognizes intrusions that have already been discovered. However, since anomalies

could just represent new normal behaviors rather than true invasions, AIDS normally creates a higher false-positive rate.

Figure 1: Signature and Anomaly-based IDS Systems

Figure 2: Signature and Anomaly-based IDS Systems WorkFlow

2.2.6. Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI) is the ability of a computer or a robot-controlled to perform tasks that normally require human knowledge and discretion. While no AI can accomplish all of the jobs that a human can, some AIs can match humans in specialized skills. Simply said, AI strives to expand and enhance mankind's ability and efficiency in operations such as rebuilding nature and regulating society via intelligent robots, with the main aim of establishing a society in which people and machines coexist peacefully. Typical examples of AI systems are SIRI from Apple and Alexa from Amazon. AI gave birth to systems that are self-learned and are called machine learning (ML) systems. ML are systems that improve over time without requiring human involvement. Machine learning (ML) applied to massive data sets is known as deep learning (DL).

2.2.6.1. Machine Learning Algorithms

Healthcare Applications of Computational Intelligence (2020) wrote that a machine learning algorithm, which is a subset of Artificial intelligence, employs a variety of precise, probabilistic, and improved methodologies to enable computers to learn from previous reference points and recognize difficult-to-perceive patterns in large, noisy, or complex datasets. Again, ML is the branch of study that allows computers to learn without being explicitly programmed, according to Arthur Samuel (1959). Examples of such algorithms are Linear regression, Logistic regression, Decision tree, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Naive Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbor, K-Means Clustering, and Random Forest algorithm just to mention a few.

Painuli et al., (2021) in a study wrote that machine learning algorithms can be broken down into the following categories: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning, and in some research, semi-supervised learning was added as a fourth type.

Supervised Learning: This approach involves predicting a target variable (or dependent variable) from a set of predictors (independent variables). We create a function that maps inputs to desired outputs using these variables. The training procedure is repeated until the model reaches the appropriate degree of accuracy on the test data. A supervisor (labels) is there to guide or correct this form of learning. Decision Trees, Random Forests, KNN, Logistic Regression, and others are examples of supervised learning.

Unsupervised Learning: There is no target or outcome variable to forecast or forecast in this method. It's utilized to segregate people into separate categories. This type does not have a supervisor to advise or correct them. When there are unlabeled or unclassified data to train the system, this type of learning algorithm is applied. The appropriate output is not specified by the system, but it examines the data in such a way that it can derive inferences (rules) from datasets and identify hidden structures in unlabeled data. Examples: K-means algorithm, Apriori algorithm.

Semi-supervised machine learning methods fall somewhere in the middle of supervised and unsupervised learning. As a result, for training purposes, this form of learning algorithm uses both unlabeled and labeled data, with a small amount of labeled data and a large number of unlabeled data. This type of approach is utilized to improve learning precision.

Reinforcement Learning: This algorithm is used to educate the machine to make judgment calls. It works like this: the machine is situated in a setting where it is constantly trained through trial and error. This computer learns from previous experiences and attempts to gather the most relevant information to make appropriate business decisions. It usually operates on a 0 to 1 scale, with 0 indicating punishment and 1 indicating reward. Markov Decision Process is an example of Reinforcement Learning.

2.2.6.2. Deep Learning Algorithms

Deep learning is critical to overcoming the problem of learning and analyzing large amounts of data. To derive useful information, it learns large data sets and concepts from raw datasets. The nature of deep learning algorithms, which demands a large quantity of training data, is also supported by big data. The accuracy of testing is improved by training many parameters in deep learning networks.

Brownlee (2019/2020) stated that Artificial neural networks are subfield deep learning focused with methods inspired by the structure and brain functions. It cuts down on feature engineering time, which is one of the most time-consuming aspects of machine learning. Its design became more change-resistant as a result of ongoing training and can now work on a variety of problems. Grover (2019/2020) mentioned Examples of such algorithms as K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Recurring Neural Networks (RNN), Deep Neural Networks (DNN), Deep Belief Network (DBN), Back Propagation, and Stochastic Gradient Descent.

2.3. Empirical Works

Masdari and Khezrib (2020) carried out a survey using a systematic literature review methodology according to studies relevant to fuzzy misuse detection techniques in the Intrusion Detecting System (IDS) and made comparisons among the different fuzzy schemes. The authors developed fuzzy intrusion detection strategies to improve penetration detection performance and manage ambiguity. They also investigated fuzzy usage detection algorithms developed using machine learning and data mining techniques to combat network invasions. They experimented with datasets such as KDD-CUP99, DARPA, NSL-KDD, and ISCX. This study compared fuzzy IDS approaches using performance evaluation variables, membership functions, FLC type, and feature

extraction methods. To have an efficient IDS, False Positive and False Negative should be reduced, while True Positive and True Negative should be maximized. The scheme was evaluated using accuracy, error state, correct state, sensitivity, false negative, precision, recall, F-measure, True positive, true negative, false positive, and F-measure. Medina et al., (2020) also worked on the correctness of a real physiological dataset obtained from a Body Area Network (WBAN) using decision tree classification methods and visualization tools. These Data Mining techniques were applied in the WBAN and a signature-based approach was then used to detect the network intrusions. The authors aimed at testing the accuracy and detection rate **to increase the network performance**. The accuracy rate and detection rate (which is serving as the performance metrics) of a genuine physiological dataset in its original form were then analyzed using the Weka software program to see if they satisfied the methodology's specified goal.

Alzahrani et al., (2020) used Support Vector Machine (SVM) methods and Structural Sparse Logistic Regression (SSPLR) to assess the significant and discriminative aspects to identify distinct attacks. In comparison to other strategies utilized for intrusion detection systems, the proposed methodologies (SVMs and SSPLR) enhanced performance (IDS). The researchers aimed to improve the performance of IDS by identifying significant and discriminative aspects of attacks. The study found that using SVM and SSPLR in combination improved the performance of IDS compared to other strategies. The researchers were able to identify the most significant and discriminative aspects of attacks, which helped to improve the accuracy of the IDS in detecting and classifying malicious activity. Overall, the study highlights the potential benefits of using machine learning algorithms such as SVM and SSPLR in IDS to improve their performance and accuracy. By identifying the most significant and discriminative aspects of attacks, researchers can develop more effective IDS that can better detect and respond to potential threats.

Su et al., (2020) proposed a model for detecting traffic anomalies called BAT. Bidirectional long short-term memory (BLSTM) and an attention mechanism were incorporated in the suggested model (BAT). High accuracy rates were attained by the suggested model, which also outperformed competing approaches. The BAT model proposed by Su et al. achieved high accuracy rates in detecting traffic anomalies and outperformed competing approaches. By incorporating BLSTM and an attention mechanism, the model was able to effectively capture the temporal and spatial characteristics of network traffic and identify anomalies in real-time. Overall, the study highlights the potential benefits of using deep learning techniques such as BLSTM and attention mechanisms in network traffic analysis. By improving the accuracy and efficiency of traffic anomaly detection, researchers can develop more effective network security systems that can better detect and respond to potential threats.

In another article, Díaz-Verdejo et al., (2022) attempted to understand much more about the consequences of employing predetermined rule sets in the **performance capabilities of signature-based intrusion systems** (SIDS) in the web context environment. The cooperative decision (a combination of the three SIDS) impacts precision and detection rates positively, while minimizing false alarm rates. An effective method was tested using Snort's rule-set in real-time life trace. The greatest detection rate achieved is insufficient to properly safeguard systems and is lower than predicted for known assaults. Combining the output of many detectors with specified configurations can improve the detection rate or accuracy of a solo SIDS. The combination of the least sensitive configurations of InspectorLog and ModSecurity increased the individual detection rates. This work was experimental and limited to HTTP URI attacks. Overall, the study highlights the importance of cooperative decision-making approaches and rule set optimization in improving the performance of SIDS in the web context environment. By combining the results of multiple SIDS and systematically deactivating unnecessary rules, researchers can develop more effective

intrusion detection systems that can better detect and prevent potential threats. Faker & Dogdu (2019) improved the performance of intrusion detection systems by combining big data and deep learning techniques. Classifiers for the network traffic datasets included Deep Feed-Forward Neural Networks (DNN) and two ensemble methods, Random Forest and Gradient Boosting Trees (GBT). The proposed technique was assessed using the UNSW NB15 and CICIDS2017 datasets. In comparison to the UNSW NB15 dataset, which had a binary classification accuracy of 99.99 percent and a multiclass classification accuracy of 99.56 percent, the suggested technique had a multiclass classification accuracy of 97.01 percent and a binary classification accuracy of 99.16 percent.

Alsadhan et al., (2019) proposed a method for detecting Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) assaults that makes advantage of flow-based network modeling. The suggested scheme outperformed previous state-of-the-art methods in terms of detection performance, having a DDoS detection accuracy of 99 percent and a replay attack detection accuracy of 91.17 percent.

Granjal et al., (2018) proposed an IDS architecture for detecting and blocking threats in CoAP communication systems with Internet integration. The suggested framework utilized anomaly-based intrusion detection and assessed its performance in identifying Denial of Service (DoS) assaults. With the multiclass problem and the binary-class problem, the proposed system has an accuracy rate of 93 percent and 92 percent, respectively. Gunay and Orman (2020) proposed an Updated Firefly Algorithm-Based Attribute Selection Method and an Artificial Immune System that uses the K-Nearest Neighbor approach, whilst the Algorithm for an Artificial Synthetic Immune System was also created using common behaviors to discover the optimum feature subset for the KDDCUP99 dataset to execute effective classification with a higher accuracy rate. The proposed firefly algorithm (PFFA) was found to have saved enough time and memory during usage

than the traditional firefly algorithm. Accuracy rate and prediction rates were the main performance metrics evaluated.

Kasongo & Sun (2020) presented a wireless intrusion detection system (IDS) using a Wrapper Based Feature Extraction Unit and a Feed-Forward Deep Neural Network (FFDNN) (WFEU). The WFEU extraction approach created a reduced ideal feature vector using the additional Trees algorithm. The suggested model was evaluated against a number of machine learning methods, including Decision Tree (DT), Naive Bayes (NB), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), and k-Nearest Neighbor (kNN). The WFEU extraction approach created a reduced ideal feature vector using the additional Trees algorithm, which helps in selecting the most important features from a large set of features. The proposed model was then evaluated against several machine learning methods, including Decision Tree (DT), Naive Bayes (NB), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), and k-Nearest Neighbor (kNN). When the WFEU produced an ideal feature vector with 22 attributes, the model's overall accuracy for binary and multiclass classification schemes was 87.10 percent and 77.16 percent, respectively. By improving the accuracy and efficiency of wireless intrusion detection, researchers can develop more effective security systems to protect wireless networks from potential threats.

Hajisalem & Babaie (2018) based on the Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) and Artificial Fish Swarm (AFS) algorithms, a novel hybrid classification technique was presented. The Fuzzy C-Means Clustering (FCM) and Correlation-based Feature Selection (CFS) approaches were used, respectively, to split the training dataset and remove pointless features. On the NSL-KDD and UNSW NB15 datasets, simulation results of the suggested technique revealed a detection rate of 99 percent and a false positive rate of 0.01 percent.

Liu et al., (2019) developed a network intrusion detection model that combines deep learning. A hierarchical attention mechanism-based bidirectional gated recurrent unit (GRU) network

intrusion detection model was presented. The proposed technique was evaluated using the UNSW NB15 dataset, which is a commonly used benchmark dataset for intrusion detection systems. The simulation results showed that the proposed model achieved a detection accuracy of more than 98.76% and a false alarm rate (FAR) of less than 1.2%. These results outperformed the results obtained by other machine learning algorithms evaluated in the study. Overall, the study demonstrates the potential of deep learning techniques in improving the performance of network intrusion detection systems. The proposed hierarchical attention mechanism-based bidirectional GRU network intrusion detection model showed promising results, indicating its effectiveness in accurately detecting network intrusions while reducing false positive rates.

Lv et al., (2020) offer a new accurate and efficient misuse intrusion detection system based on an extreme learning machine with a hybrid kernel function (HKELM), which relies on particular attack signatures to distinguish between legitimate and malicious operations. The HKELM approach used in the proposed system combines two different kernel functions, namely the radial basis function (RBF) and the polynomial kernel. This hybrid kernel function is used to improve the accuracy and efficiency of the extreme learning machine-based intrusion detection system. The proposed system was evaluated using two commonly used benchmark datasets for intrusion detection, namely the UNSW NB15 and KDD99 datasets. The simulation results showed that the proposed HKELM-based system achieved high accuracy rates in detecting network intrusions. Specifically, the proposed system achieved an accuracy rate of 99.53% and 99.88% on the UNSW NB15 and KDD99 datasets, respectively. Overall, the study demonstrates the potential of extreme learning machine-based intrusion detection systems with a hybrid kernel function in accurately and efficiently detecting network intrusions. The proposed HKELM-based system showed promising results in detecting network intrusions with high accuracy rates, indicating its potential use in real-world intrusion detection applications.

Einy et al., (2021) created Suricata using a neural network (NN) model for metaheuristic (fuzzy logic) neural network detection of hostile traffic and was used as the Intrusion Detection System/Intrusion Prevention System. Suricata is an anomaly and pattern-based system security in detecting internal and external assaults, intrusions, or anomalous activities. Thus, the suggested method aims to handle intrusions in a network with a **higher accuracy rate**. The method showed good accuracy in detecting and preventing attacks on the targeted network, capable of detecting SMB exploits, SQL injections, XSS attacks, and brute force attacks. The execution time was within the expected response time, even though it can only analyze a limited number of datasets. Performance metrics were evaluated using precision, false-positive ratio, and accuracy rates.

Jiang et al., (2020) introduced a network intrusion detection technique that incorporates deep hierarchical networks and hybrid sampling. By using the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique, One-side Selection (OSS) was employed to increase the minority samples and decrease the noise samples in the majority category (SMOTE). On the NSL-KDD and UNSW-NB15 datasets, the suggested network intrusion detection algorithm was tested, and the results showed classification accuracy of 83.58 and 77.16 percent, respectively.

Again, a machine learning-based hybrid classification Model for a feasible and effective intrusion detection scheme was proposed by Kumar et al., (2020) **aimed at producing low false alarm rates with very high accuracy** in Software-Defined Networking architecture (SDN). The highest accuracy was attained using the random forest method with the feature selection technique of Gain Ratio, Symmetric Uncertainty, and the Chi-square Test. In their exploration, they analyzed the standard NSL-KDD dataset for predicting possible intrusion by using some effective classification methods like J48, Random Forest (RF), Theory of Projective Adaptive Resonance (PART), Naive Bayes, Decision Table (DT), and Radial Basis Function Network (RBFN), and Bayesian Network. The dataset used in the method minimizes redundancies between the training dataset and the

testing dataset. From their experiment, it is clear that Random Forest shows a high test accuracy compared with all other algorithms therefore for flow-based anomaly detection, the use of RF is essential to achieve high accuracy and speed up the process of intrusion detection in SDN. Accuracy, TP rate, FP rate, Precision, Recall, False alarm rate, F-measure, Mathews correlation coefficient (MCC), and Means absolute error (MAE) were the evaluation metrics.

In another article, an Intruding Detection System that is Hybrid (HIDS) was created by Khraisat et al., (2020) through the combination of a C5 decision tree classifier and a One-Class Support Vector Machine (OC-SVM) to identify both the well-known intrusions and zero-day attacks to **achieve high detection accuracy, precision, low false-alarm rates, and recall.** In comparison to Signature-based IDS and Anomaly-based IDS, the HIDS performs better than predicted concerning its detection rate and small false-alarm rates, according to their research. In terms of total performance, the Hybrid IDS thus outperforms other approaches. In terms of detection rates, precision, false alarm rates, true negative rates, false-positive rates, sensitivity, false-negative rates, recall, specificity, and Frequency Measure, it was demonstrated that a combination of the C5 classifier (misuse) and the one-class SVM (anomaly) can give higher detection rate when it is been compared with several other machine learning methods.

In another article where the authors are looking to successfully detect anomalous behaviors presumably caused by hostile activities, Kwon et al., (2022) suggested a hybrid anomaly detection approach that incorporates statistical filtering with a composite autoencoder. Their goal was **to construct a dependable and effective anomaly detection system** for real-time system monitoring. SQL injection attacks, Cross-Site Scripting (XSS) assaults, weak authentication, and any ransomware payload were the main targets. The method was found to detect more anomalies than the autoencoder-only detection approach but still gave more false alarms during run time.

Thus the hybrid system suggested gave better results. To assess its performance, True Positive (TP), False Positive (FP), False Negative (FN) rates, True Negative (TN), and Precision were used.

Alazzam et al., (2020) proposed a new algorithm for feature selection for a system that detects intrusions on a pigeon-inspired optimizer **to decrease the quantity of features** needed to build a robust IDS while simultaneously maintaining a higher detection rate and accuracies with low false alarms. Using the KDDCUP99, NLS-KDD, and UNSW-NB15 datasets, the new method for binarizing a continuous pigeon-inspired optimizer was compared to the old method to binarize continual algorithms for swarm intelligence. In terms of True Positive Rates, False Positive Rates, and accuracies, the suggested approach beat numerous feature selection techniques from state-of-the-art related research. Also, a new method for discretizing a continuous problem based on cosine similarity was carried out to accelerate the process of convergence. This feature selection method used increases accuracy, training, and testing speed. It also reduces processing costs, minimizes storage space, and increases understanding of the test data. Performance metrics like true positive, false positive, and accuracies were examined.

An optimized swarm intelligence algorithm (KH algorithm) based on the linear nearest neighbor lasso step (LNNLS-KH) for feature selection was proposed by Li et al., (2021) to solve the challenge of intrusion detection datasets with a huge number and high dimensions. The individual krills' physical dispersion motion was modified by accelerating the convergence speed of the nonlinear approach. The experiments conducted made use of NSL-KDD and CICIDS2017 datasets on average, this basically removes features that are superfluous while ensuring high detection accuracy. The LNNLS-KH algorithm in terms of performance outperformed the competition of intrusion detection assessment indicators. The exploration capabilities of the KH algorithm are insufficient, which means that while tackling practical problems, the algorithm is prone to falling

into a locally optimal solution. Evaluation metrics such as False positive, True positive, False negative, True negative, and Detection rates were conducted to find the optimal solution.

Almaslukh (2021) proposed a model from deep learning (the Artificial Neural Network) and an entity embedding-based to handle various intrusions like backhole, gray holes, and flooding making use of the WSN-DS simulated dataset. Wireless Sensor Networks have limited computing resources, power, and storage, they are more vulnerable to such attacks. The method was **aimed at a more precise detection classification algorithm** and also to implement entity embedding to transform raw features into a robust model. In terms of precision, false positives, and recall, our Deep Learning and Entity Embedding-Based Intrusion Detection Model for Wireless Sensor Networks performs well. The method had one major flaw: it used raw features to develop an intrusion detection model, which can lead to low detection accuracy.

Dushimimana et al., (2020) proposed and applied a Bidirectional Recurrent Neural Network (BRNN) methodology to build a security solution with **high durability** for IoT network security. **Feature selection mechanisms** were also implemented to help identify and remove non-essential variables from data that do not affect the accuracy of the prediction model. A machine learning approach that allows production without hyperparameter tuning has been developed by researchers at the University of Bristol. The Random Forest (RF) algorithm was implemented over Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to obtain a more precise and consistent prediction. The aim was to investigate the application of deep learning by having multiple layers and hybrid layers of different architectures in one framework, as well as deploying these techniques in IoT applications to develop robust security solutions. The results of this research revealed that BRNN stands up and outperforms other algorithms like the normal Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) and Gated recurrent neural network (GRNN) with an accuracy of 99.04%. It also overcomes the gap missing from the Gated recurrent neural network and RNN. Important metrics such as Precision, Accuracy,

Recall, False positive, True positive, false negative, true negative, and False Alarm Rate (FAR) were calculated.

Chung and Xu (2021) also proposed a lightweight signature-based intrusion detection system for Electronic Control Units in In-Vehicle CAN Bus networks in real-world scenarios. The approach may effectively detect CAN traffic-related anomalies, according to experimental data. The detection ratio for content-related abnormalities can be increased by utilizing the relationship between the signals. Simulation data demonstrate that the proposed IDS could effectively detect drop and replay attacks. The proposed method was shown to be more flexible and require less computation time. The method could still not cover all attack types at their full strength, thus achieving quite a low detection rate. Despite this, the suggested IDS can be used in resource-constrained in-vehicle ECUs and will be capable of detecting all attack modalities.

Furthermore, Onyedeké et al., (2020) took an object-oriented approach to analysis and design (OOADM) in the modeling and development of the smart intrusion detection system using actual intrusion characteristics and methods for more flexible and effective detection of invasions. The goal of the model was to **raise users' awareness of the high rate of intrusions or malware on Android phones, as well as a countermeasure solution for more secure operations**. The model was also focused on identifying malicious intrusions on smartphones, through fingerprint and password validity and also taking a selfie of the unknown intruder, and keeping logs for the user. As a result, the method was discovered to be more flexible and efficient in detecting intrusions. The issue of the false alarm was averted due to the projected system major alert agent being through SMS, MMS, and not an e-mail that requires ICMP.

A variety of Detection methods for cyberattacks based on deep learning and machine learning on the next-generation 5G systems were explored once again by Borgesen and Kholidy (2020). The goal of their research was to **minimize the computing resource requirements** for the different

machine learning and deep learning models and also **optimize the ease of use of these models**. Four different machine learning and deep learning approaches namely the Naïve Bayes model, logistic regression model, decision tree model, and the random forest model were evaluated using the AWID dataset. The Random Forest model is less computationally expensive to train and does not require a GPU. The model was simple to use and faster in execution. The Random Forest algorithm was fast, easy to use, and also achieved the best performance with default parameters. The performance was evaluated using the true positive and false positive as metrics.

Bhandari et al., (2020) proposed that using a smaller feature subset to save execution time and enhance classification accuracy, the Shapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) algorithm and the tree-based classifier algorithms were combined. According to this research, decreasing the number of features allows classification techniques to concentrate on critical characteristics that distinguish "attack" groups. Random Forest, XGBoost, LightGBM, and CatBoost provide similar or improved results in terms of accuracy, precision, and recall when applied to a reduced feature subset. Using a smaller feature subset enhances the accuracy and efficiency of IDS. There were attenuation distribution differences between the training and the testing datasets. Accuracy, precision, and recall were the performance metrics evaluated.

Zhou et al., (2020) applied a heuristic approach called CFS-BA, and they created an efficient intrusion detecting system based on feature selection in conjunction with the ensemble classifier to select the optimum subset determined via feature correlation; the ensemble approach combines C4.5, Random Forest (RF), and Forest by Penalizing Attributes (Forest PA) algorithms. The method was finalized with the voting technique for attack recognition. The goal was to achieve higher accuracy and small false alarms by making use of NSL-KDD, AWID, and CIC-IDS2017 datasets. The solution shows outstanding performance in terms of Accuracy Detection Rate in comparison with other classification algorithms, and the comparison results with the state-of-the-

art methods indicate that the suggested CFS-BA-Ensemble technique can provide a powerful competitive advantage in the intrusion detection domain. Combining the individual classifiers in this way gives a better classification of objects and reduces bias among different training datasets even though the method is incapable of detecting rare attacks from massive network traffic.

An integrated approach of the machine learning model and a knowledge-based system was proposed by Chiche and Meshesha (2021) to **create a scalable and adaptive nature of learning to detect network attacks or intrusions**. Experiments show that whenever the dataset is updated, the system is also automatically updating the model such that the new pattern is also considered during the next prediction stage, and this makes the system scalable and adaptive. The random forest outperforms the other two classifiers in terms of identifying attacks, according to the empirical results. The results also reveal that, when compared to SMO and Bayes Net, the random forest (RF) has greater accuracy for detecting Normal, DoS, Probe, and R2L assaults, but it has the worst accuracy for detecting U2R attacks. The unavailability of instant data to test the approach is still a limitation of the methodology. Classification accuracy, true positive rate, false-positive rate, precision, recall, and sensitivity ratio were some evaluation metrics implored in the article.

An improved version of the Internet Protocol Flow Information Export (IPFIX) Signature-based Intrusion Detection System (FIXIDS) was proposed by Erlacher and Dressler (2020) to do high-speed signature-based intrusion detection **whilst detecting larger events**. HTTP intrusion signatures are used by FIXIDS (that is the Snort-Compatible Signatures) from the common Snort System using them to inbound IPFIX-Conforming HTTP Flows. The evaluation showed that FIXIDS has the same detection accuracy as Snort. In their functional evaluation, the authors found out that the methods and algorithms implemented in FIXIDS work as expected and thus accurately and precisely detect a wider variety of events in the analyzed network traffic. In comparison to

Snort, the authors found that FIXIDS can handle four times more network traffic without dropping while keeping the same event detection rate. In high-speed networks with low performance, FIXIDS delivers exact event detection.

Therefore, the Weka software program was used to create models as quickly as possible, then guide you through the finer points of developing predictive models for classification modeling problems, detect intrusions in the UNSW-NB15 dataset, analyze these machine learning techniques, and compare their performances. Weka is a library of data mining algorithms used in data mining tasks. The Weka software is an open-source program designed for data mining and analysis using machine learning and deep learning methods. It includes a variety of tools for data preparation, categorization, regression, cluster analysis, case-based reasoning, and visualization.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1. Overview

Several strategies are used in network environments to recognize and classify network intrusions. This chapter outlines a modeled system for determining if intrusions have occurred, for identifying them when they do, and for classifying them in light of the attack types that have been researched. The experimental processes go into great detail on the methodologies used.

3.2. Proposed Framework

The figure below shows the suggested framework, which details the steps required to build and test the ML model.

Figure 3: The proposed framework.

3.2.1. Dataset Selection

For both training and testing purposes in this study, the UNSW-NB15 dataset is employed. The ability of anomaly detection to spot fresh assaults has drawn the attention of many researchers. The intricacy of these systems has prevented their widespread usage in practical applications, though, as they require extensive testing, analyzing, and tuning before deployment. The idealistic testing and evaluation process for these systems comprises subjecting them to a comprehensive and extensive collection of intrusions and aberrant behavior while running them across real tagged network traces. This data collection combines contemporary synthetic network traffic attack activities with real-world modern normal behavior. The features of the UNSWNB15 data collection are produced using both established and new methodologies. Husain et al., (2019) claim that when compared to the KddCup99 dataset, the UNSW NB15 dataset more accurately captures contemporary network attacks and network traffic. Additionally, the Kdd99 dataset's properties are less effective than those of the UNSW NB15 dataset (Moustafa & Slay, 2015). The datasets UNSW NB15 (Faker & Dogdu, 2019), NSL-KDD (Mehmood et al., (2018), and KddCup99 (Faker & Dogdu, 2019) are often used for network intrusion detection, Sharma et al., (2019). The CAIDA dataset (Manso, Moura, & Serrão, 2019), the WSN-DS dataset (Almomani & Alenez, 2018), and the Gas pipeline dataset are other datasets that are taken into consideration for use in identifying network intrusions (Al-Hawawreh, Sitnikova, & Den Hartog, 2019).

3.2.2. Software Tools and Hardware Platform

3.2.2.1. The Weka Workbench/Software

A collection of machine learning algorithms for data mining tasks is called Weka (Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis), and it was developed at the University of Waikato in New Zealand. It is distributed as free software and adheres to the GNU (General Public License). The

algorithms can be used directly on a dataset or used from your own Java code. Weka offers tools and functions for pre-processing data, feature selection, regression, clustering, association rules, classification, and data visualization. Following initialization, the WEKA GUI chooser gives the user the option to select one of the five types of programs listed below:

- Explorer
- Experimenter
- KnowledgeFlow
- Workbench
- Simple CLI

Source: Experimental Analysis 2022

Benefits of utilizing the Weka Data Mining Software

These procedures are included in the WEKA tool:

- Examining and pre-processing the database's features, as well as determining whether the data is accurate.
- Definition of the class attributes that categorize the collection of instances into the correct classes.
- Extraction of the potential classification-relevant characteristics.
- Choosing a subset of features to be applied during learning.
- Investigation into any imbalances in the chosen data collection and possible solutions.
- Choosing a subset of the occurrences, or the data that will serve as the foundation for learning.
- Utilizing a classifier method to aid in learning.
- Choosing a testing strategy to gauge how well the chosen algorithm will function.

Weka Data Mining's Principal Benefits

A company can genuinely achieve its full potential with the aid of Weka data mining. It is a means to evaluate the effects that particular traits are having on a company and could aid business owners in increasing profits and averting mistakes in the future. In essence, a company employs this technique to look at specific data from several perspectives to get a whole picture of how its operations are developing. Owners of businesses can obtain a thorough understanding of topics including client trends, prospective income leakage, and potential money makers. The information might also highlight methods for a business to cut wasteful expenses and perhaps boost overall revenue.

Characteristics of Weka Data Mining

The computer program Weka data mining can assist any company in reviewing and analyzing its data more effectively. By giving customers the option to individually review their data from

several engaging angles, it may communicate with users amicably. With the help of the Weka data mining tool, the user can also identify relationships and trends between his data and that of others in several other regional directories.

3.2.2.2. Hardware Platform

This experiment will be carried out on a Windows 10 laptop with an Intel(R) Core (TM) i7 processor running at 2.80GHz and 16GB of installed primary memory.

3.2.3. Design Science Research Methodology

The goal of design science methodology is to produce novel and creative items that push the limits of organizational and human capabilities. In order to address issues found in companies, design science also creates and evaluates IT artifacts that may differ from formal logic, software, and rigorous mathematics (Hevner, March, Park, & Ram, 2004).

3.2.4. Data Acquisition

The collecting of the dataset needed for the experiment—the first step in the identification of network intrusions—takes place. During the initial step of network intrusion detection, the dataset must be collected. The dataset was obtained by downloading it from the internet to carry out this. Use the following URL to obtain the UNSW NB15 dataset from Github in .ARFF format: [https://github.com/InitRoot/UNSW NB15/blob/master/UNSW NB15.zip](https://github.com/InitRoot/UNSW-NB15/blob/master/UNSW-NB15.zip).

3.2.5. Data Information

Network intrusion dataset UNSW-NB15 is sometimes referred to as UNSQ-NB15. It was developed by the IXIA PerfectStorm tool in the Cyber Range Lab of the Australian Centre for Cyber Security (ACCS) to provide a hybrid of real-world, contemporary normal behaviors and synthetic, modern attack behaviors (Moustafa & Slay, 2015). The UNSW NB15 dataset consists

of 175341 unique data sets with 44 unique attributes. 175,341 records make up the training set, while 82,332 records from the attack and normal types make up the testing set.

Flow features, basic features, content features, temporal features, and further generated features are the several categories into which the features of the UNSW NB15 dataset are divided. The features of the UNSW NB15 dataset are listed in Table 1. The dataset is shown in broad strokes in Figure 5. Backdoors, Denial of Service (DoS), Fuzzers, Worms, Reconnaissance, Generic, Exploits, Analysis, and Shellcode are the nine different assaults in this dataset. The numerous attacks are defined in Table 2.

Table 1: The UNSW NB15 dataset's characteristics

S/N	Name	Type	Description
1.	srcip	Nominal	The IP address of the source
2.	sport	Integer	Port number of source
3.	dstip	Nominal	The IP address of the destination
4.	Dsport	Integer	Port number of destination
5.	Proto	Nominal	Transaction protocol
6.	state	Nominal	Indicates to the state and its dependent protocol, e.g. ACC, CLO, CON, ECO, ECR, FIN, INT, MAS, PAR, REQ, RST, TST, TXD, URH, URN, and (-) (if not used state)
7.	Dur	Float	Total duration record
8.	sbytes	integer	Bytes used in transactions from source to destination
9.	Dbytes	integer	Transaction bytes from source to destination
10.	Sttl	integer	originating time to live value
11.	Dttl	integer	Value of the destination time to live
12.1	Sloss	integer	retransmitted or dropped source packets

13.	Dloss	integer	Dropped or retransmitted Destination packets
14.	Service	nominal	HTTP, FTP, SMTPSSH, DNS, FTP-DATA, IRC, and (-) if the service is not frequently used
15.	Sload	Float	Bits per second of the source
16.	Dload	Float	Bits per second at the destination
17.	Spkts	integer	number of packets from source to destination
18.	Dpkts	integer	Packet count from source to destination
19.	Swin	integer	Value of source TCP window advertising
20.	dwin	integer	Value of the Destination TCP window's advertisements
21.	Stcpb	integer	The source TCP base's sequence number
22.	Dtcpb	Integer	The destination TCP base's sequence number
23.	Smeansz	Integer	The average row packet size sent by the src
24.	dmeansz	Integer	The average row packet size sent by the dst
25.	trans_depth	integer	represents the depth of the http request/response transaction's pipelined connection.
26.	res_bdy_len	integer	Actual content size of the data transferred from the server's http service.
27.	Sjit	Float	Source jitter (mSec)
28.	Djit	Float	Destination jitter (mSec)
29.	Stime	Timestamp	start time record
30.	Ltime	Timestamp	last time record
31.	Sintpkt	Float	Interpacket arrival time of Source (mSec)
32.	Dintpkt	Float	Interpacket arrival time of Destination (mSec)

33.	Tcprtt	Float	Round-trip time for setting up a TCP connection, comprised of "synack" and "ackdat."
34.	synack	Float	the interval between SYN and SYN ACK packets in a TCP connection.
35.	ackdat	Float	The interval between SYN ACK and ACK packets in a TCP connection.
36.	is_sm_ips_ports	Binary	This variable takes value one (1) if the source (1), destination (3), and port numbers (2), (4), are all equal. Otherwise, it takes value zero (0).
37.	ct_state_ttl	Integer	Number according to the precise range of values for the source/destination time to live (10) for each state (11).
38.	ct_flw_http_mthd	integer	Number of flows in the http service that use methods like Get and Post.
39.	is_ftp_login	Binary	If the user and password are used to access the FTP session, then 1; else, 0.
40.	ct_ftp_cmd	Integer	the quantity of flows with commands in an ftp session.
41.	ct_srv_src	integer	In 100 connections, the last time there were 14 connections with the same service and 1 connection with the same source address (26).
42.	ct_srv_dst	integer	In 100 connections, there are now 14 connections with the same service and 3 connections with the same destination address (26).
43.	ct_dst_ltm	integer	According to the most recent data, there were three connections with the same destination address out of every 100 connections (26).

44.	ct_src_ltm	integer	One connection from the same source address out of every 100 made, according to the most recent data (26).
45.	ct_src_dport_ltm	integer	In 100 connections, there were 1 connections with the same source address and 4 connections with the same destination port (26).
46.	ct_dst_sport_ltm	integer	According to the most recent instance, there were three connections with the same destination address and two with the same source port for every 100 connections (26).
47.	ct_dst_src_ltm	integer	In 100 connections, there were (1) connections with the same source address and (3) connections with the same destination address (26).
48.	attack_cat	nominal	the title of each assault type. Nine categories, including, for example, Analysis, Backdoors, Generic DoS Exploits, Reconnaissance, Shellcode, and Worms.

Figure 5: Description of the features of the UNSW_NB15 dataset (Kumar et al., 2019)

3.2.6. Data Preprocessing

This step is the next in the process of detecting intrusions and any harmful activity. This stage includes data cleansing, randomization, and feature/dimensionality reduction. Building a machine learning model requires the preparation of the data. This is because a machine learning method's performance is influenced by how effectively the dataset is prepared and structured (Ali, et al., 2021). The obtained dataset (the UNSW NB15 dataset) has undergone preprocessing to ensure that the data is clean. Normalization, randomization, and dimension reduction using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) are all carried out as part of the dataset's preprocessing.

Data Cleaning (Standardize, Randomize, Normalize)

Data cleaning entails locating and improving, replacing, or eliminating irrelevant, false, and incomplete data. You will find numerous functions to utilize in cleaning the dataset if you select unsupervised in the Filter section of the Preprocess tab. As noted in the section, this project used a few of them.

1. Mean values are used to fill in any missing data.. Choose ReplaceMissingValues from the unsupervised folder of the Filter section under the Preprocess tab.
2. RemoveDuplicates
3. The mean values are substituted for some infinity values in the two columns Flow Bytes and Flow Pkts /s.
4. The Time Stamp columns should be removed because they serve no purpose.

Figure 6: The picture above shows duplicate values been removed through the data cleaning process

Data Standardization: By setting the mean and standard deviation to 0 and 1, respectively, data standardization is employed to guarantee that the feature value ranges are homogeneous. Values above the mean change from negative to positive, and vice versa.

Data normalization involves scaling and shifting real-valued numerical properties or values into the range between 0 and 1. (Brownlee, 2014).

Data randomization is a widely used method that can improve the accuracy of research data and reduce fraud.

Dimensionality Reduction using Principal Component Analysis

The feature extraction stage is another name for this phase. The features that will feed into the machine learning models for network intrusion are selected at this point. Devi (2019) used a general feature and a subset of features as the foundation for the feature selection. The roles chosen to establish the identification of the feature, including whether it was common, distinctive, labeled, etc.

By splitting up a big set of associated features into a smaller set of less correlated features called principle components, principal component analysis (PCA) is used to reduce the dimensionality of datasets while retaining the majority of the data from the original dataset. Because smaller datasets are simpler to process, dimensionality reduction trades off accuracy for simplicity. The accuracy of a classification model may decline with a reduced number of features. Thus, the project used data cleansing techniques, but it was careful to avoid abusing their predicted accuracies by using them excessively.

The following steps comprise PCA. The first step is to standardize the values of the dataset's features using the WEKA platform's default standardization. In WEKA, PCA is accessible from the preprocess panel's unsupervised folder. PCA employs a rank filter that ranks the features from highest to lowest. To choose features independently of any predictor, the filter approach depends on the general properties of the training data by Sanchez-Marono et al., (2007). Using Weka, the filter approach was applied to the dataset.

Source: Experimental Analysis 2022

Figure 7: PCA feature reduction in WEKA.

Table 2: The UNSW NB15 dataset's definitions of the various attacks; Kumar et al., (2020)

Attack Type	Description
Backdoor	Bypassing the authentication process in this manner allows illegal access to any network.
Denial of Service (DoS)	This attack prevents resources from being made available to the real user's request by interfering with network services.
Fuzzers	In order to wreck the network and find security holes, the attacker does this by flooding it with random data.

Worms	When malicious scripts are duplicated and an attacker attempts to access the system utilizing some weaknesses, the attack takes place.
Reconnaissance	This is the method used to obtain information about a network only for the goal of evading security measures.
Generic	The perpetrator of this attack doesn't give a damn about how primitive cryptographic operations are carried out.
Exploits	This is an attack when the perpetrator takes advantage of network vulnerabilities.
Analysis	This kind of assault utilizes spam emails, web scripts, and other methods against web applications.
Shellcode	In order to get control of the computer, this assault involves injecting scripts into an application to start a command shell.

Source: Experimental Analysis 2022

3.2.7. Model Building and Testing

The UNSW NB15 dataset is used in this step to train and test the models, and only a small number of features have been chosen through dimensionality reduction and data cleaning. The performance of the classifiers is evaluated during training and testing using ten-fold and five-fold cross-validation. The results were also evaluated and contrasted with the cross-validation using an 80:20 split. Despite cross-validating the project's actual procedure. In this project's Weka Workbench, the UNSW-NB15 dataset is uploaded in order to develop models for classification modeling issues and to ascertain the accessibility of various attacks. The network dataset was then examined for

various irregularities. Using performance evaluation metrics, it was also determined how effective these algorithms were.

3.3. Machine Learning

Machine learning (ML), a subfield of artificial intelligence (AI), enables learning without explicit programming. Its foundations are in computational mathematics, data mining, and statistics. A dataset is used to train machine learning (ML) algorithms, which then use those patterns to predict the future. IDSs frequently make use of ML. ML algorithms can be broken down into three groups: reinforcement learning, unsupervised learning, and supervised learning. Only supervised learning techniques are used in this thesis. In the project, the terms "classifiers," "techniques," and "algorithms" are all used synonymously to denote the same thing.

3.4. The types of ML algorithms

3.4.1. Unsupervised Learning

Unsupervised learning is a machine learning (ML) technique used to find hidden patterns in a dataset that contains unlabeled data. As a result, the model can be trained without labels, but the outputs are less precise than with supervised learning. When data is needed to get desired results, such as when a business needs to identify the target market for a recently introduced product, unsupervised learning is appropriate. For grouping and dimensionality reduction issues, unsupervised learning is applied. The Hidden Markov model, K-means clustering, and Gaussian mixture models are a few unsupervised learning algorithms.

3.4.2. Reinforcement Learning

A model can learn from the feedback it receives from its experiences and behaviors using a machine learning (ML) technique known as reinforcement learning. It is similar to the way people

think and take in information from their environment. Reinforcement learning is frequently used in resource management, video games, and business simulation. The well-known reinforcement learning methods are Deep Adversarial Networks, Q-learning, and Temporal Difference.

3.4.3. Supervised Learning

Supervised learning is a series of machine learning (ML) approaches used to find the creation of computational models that can automatically categorize new sets of unobserved data using patterns learned from explained data (Granjal, Silva, & Lourenço, 2018). The effectiveness of supervised learning algorithms is influenced by the caliber of the data and the model configuration parameters. Supervised learning is the most used machine learning method. It is the simplest approach to take. On labeled data, a supervised machine learning algorithm is trained to produce the required output by receiving feedback on whether the anticipated output is accurate or inaccurate. Once the algorithm has been properly trained, it can observe fresh examples and predict labels. Task-oriented learning, commonly referred to as supervised learning, The classification of spam, face recognition, and the popularity of advertisements are only a few examples of the various uses for this kind of learning. Two categories of supervised learning are discernible.

Regression: methods for predicting continuous quantities, including price, age, and pay.

Classification: algorithms that determine if something is true or untrue or whether it is spam. There are two types of classification: binary and multi-class. Linear Regression, Naive Bayes, Decision Trees, KNN, Neural Networks, and SVM are a few examples of supervised learning algorithms.

For the purposes of detecting intrusions, the UNSW-NB15 dataset was subjected to the supervised machine learning techniques K-Nearest-Neighbour (kNN), Decision tree (J48), Random Forest

(RF), and BayesNet. These models might have been created using Support Vector Machines, Regression, or Neural Networks, among other ML learning strategies.

3.4.3.1. WHY CHOOSE THESE ALGORITHMS

KNN is a non-parametric model, in contrast to linear regression, Naive Bayes, and logistic regression, which are parametric models, hence it was chosen for this study as opposed to other machine learning techniques. Additionally, the KNN method allows for non-linear solutions, unlike the Logistic Regression technique, which only allows for linear solutions. KNN outperforms linear regression when the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the input data is high. Additionally, Neural Networks require a lot more hyperparameter adjustment than KNN because they require a lot more training data than KNN. Compared to neural networks, **Random Forest** is less expensive to compute and does not require a GPU for training. A random forest can more accurately and differently interpret a decision tree. Neural networks require a lot more data than the average person could possess in order to be truly efficient.

For categorical and continuous data analysis, the **J48 method** is superior. J48 also provides more precise findings than logistic regression. Unlike Logistic Regression, which fits a single line to perfectly dividing the space into two, Decision Trees segment the region into successively smaller portions. Decision tree classifiers' widespread appeal is a result of their quick performance and straightforward design. It addresses the issues with missing values, pruning, calculating error rates, and producing rules from the trees (Witten, Frank, & Hall, 1999) looked at J48 is also useful for predicting the data's structure and for explaining the patterns in the data. If I create a Bayesian model of a medical diagnosis system, I can explain to doctors (and regulators) how the model works and the information, evidence, or knowledge that underpins each component of the model. This is not possible with neural models that are black boxes. The fundamental advantage of Bayesian networks over neural networks is the capacity to infer causal links.

3.5. Data Splitting

How to use the data at hand is a crucial decision. K-fold cross-validation and percentage split are the most widely used methods for dividing the data for training and testing. The data is divided into training and test sets using a quick and easy method called percentage split. The split ratios used most frequently are 80:20 and 70:30. The model is created using the training data, and it is assessed using the test data. Prior to testing, the test set should not be used as this can skew the findings and impair model evaluation. The data for this project is divided into training and test sets. Options for percentage split and cross-validation were both used. It is a method of data resampling that is frequently employed in ML. Because cross-validation generates less biased results than % split, it was chosen. While the percentage split had an 80:20 split ratio, the cross-validation was carried out using 10-fold and 5-fold iterations.

3.6. Machine Learning Classifiers – Classification Model

The ML classifiers used in this project are described below.

3.6.1. K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) Algorithm

The K-Nearest Neighbor method is one of the algorithms used to detect intrusions (KNN). The K-nearest Neighbor Classification Algorithm is a theoretically developed, extremely simple data mining algorithm. The KNN ML method takes into account the nearest neighbors. KNN can be used to solve problems involving classification and regression. Since the entire dataset is used during the testing stage, it is sometimes referred to as instance-based learning or lazy learning. The learning and classification algorithm KNN is sample-based. The k-nearest neighbor classification algorithm assumes that a sample belongs to a category if the majority of its K-nearest neighbor samples also fall into that category (Li W. , Yi, Wu, Pan, & Li, 2014). The closest criterion might

be the Euclidean distance of the feature vector, and the term "nearest neighbor" refers to a single or multiple feature vector that is used to describe the sample.

As a result, testing is expensive and slow. KNN makes use of neighbors' majority votes and feature similarity. The prediction result received the most votes among the classes. KNN has drawbacks including high storage needs, computational complexity, and inability to handle missing values.

3.6.2. Random Forest (RF) Algorithm

An ML classifier called Random Forest (RF) uses numerous decision trees on various dataset subsets and averages the outcomes to increase prediction accuracy. A condition is compared with one or more properties of the input data at each treenode. To get the findings, RF gathers predictions from various decision trees rather than relying solely on one. Each tree casts a vote for a specific class, and the class receiving the most votes is the projected class. On unbalanced datasets, RF performs admirably, and there aren't many classification mistakes.

3.6.3. J48 Decision Tree Algorithm

Based on different attribute values of the available data, a predictive machine learning model known as the J48 Decision tree selects the target value of a new sample. In a decision tree, the internal nodes stand in for the distinguishing characteristics, the branches between the nodes show potential values for these characteristics in the observed samples, and the terminal nodes show the dependent variable's final value (classification). To categorize a new object using the J48 technique, a decision tree based on the attribute values of the available training data must first be built. Thus, as soon as it makes touch with a collection of items, the characteristic that most obviously sets the other cases apart is detected (the training set). Since it can correctly identify the data, it is said that this characteristic offers the greatest information gain. Now, out of all the potential values for this feature, if there is one for which there is no ambiguity, meaning that all

data instances falling under its type have the same value for the goal variable, then we end that branch and assign it the target value.

3.6.4. Bayesian Network (Bayes Net) Algorithm

A probabilistic model called a Bayesian Network (Bayes Net) uses a graphical layout to resolve difficult issues. It offers information on a field where each node corresponds to a collection of random variables and each edge to a statistical link between those variables. Additionally, each node's related random variables are connected to a conditional probability distribution. Conditions or states might be part of the random variable. Probabilistic causal links are represented using the Bayes Net system.

CHAPTER FOUR

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION, RESULTS, AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Introduction

This study aims to create machine-learning models for network intrusion detection. Additionally, it sought to find attacks in a specific network dataset. This section includes information about the machine learning models' implementation, evaluation, and discussion of the outcomes.

4.2. Model Development/Implementation

The UNSW NB15 dataset is used as the working dataset in the Network Intrusion Detection System Models, which seek to assist in the detection of intrusion in a network. The Weka machine learning workbench is used to train four models: K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Random Forest

(RF), J48, and Bayes Network. These models are developed and tested using a contemporary network dataset. The choice of the Weka Simulation tool to be utilized for this purpose is the first stage in the modeling of the network intrusion detection system models.

4.3. Performance Evaluation

Here, experimental findings for K-Nearest Neighbor, Random Forest, J48, and BayesNet, four supervised machine learning algorithms, are presented. The hardware and software specifications listed in the table below were used in the experiments, which were carried out on a laptop for personal use.

Item	Specification Manufacturer Computer
Model	HP EliteBook
Operating System	Professional Windows 10
System Type	32-bit CPU, 64-bit operating system
Processor Type	2.80GHz Intel(R) Core (TM) i7-7600 CPU
Installed Memory (RAM)	16 GB @ 2133MHz
Processor Speed	3.27 GHz
Number of Cores	2
Logical Processors (Threads)	4
Machine Learning Tool	WEKA version 3.9.6

Table 3: The hardware and software parameters.

4.4. Evaluation Metrics

The performance of the machine learning algorithms in the detection of anomalies is assessed using fundamental performance scoring criteria, such as precision and recall. ML models operate on the tenet of helpful feedback. Models are created, reviewed using metrics, and adjusted as needed to increase performance. Regression, classification, clustering, and ranking all use different metrics. The performance criteria that were utilized in this study to rate the ML classifiers for intrusion detection are described below. The confusion matrix's elements are used to evaluate the evaluation metrics. The confusion matrix is a $N * N$ matrix, where N is the total number of classes.

The **precision ratio** is the sum of the true positives and false positives.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

where false positive (fp) is the number of times benign conditions were mistakenly classified as attacks and true positive (tp) is the number of attacks that were accurately identified as attacks.

Recall is the proportion of true positive responses to the total of false negative and true positive responses.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

where false negative (fn) is the number of incorrect classifications of an attack as benign.

The percentage of incidents in a dataset that were correctly classified as an attack or benign is known as **accuracy**.

$$Accuracy = \frac{(TN + TP)}{(TN + TP + FN + FP)}$$

where true negative (tn) is the number of correct classifications of benign as benign.

The recall and precision are combined to form the weighted harmonic mean, or **F-Measure**.

$$F - Measure = \frac{2TP}{2TP + FP + FN}$$

The amount of time needed to train and test the classification model is called **execution time**.

Accuracy, precision, recall, and F-measure are all reported as percentages in the performance evaluation.

4.5. Classification Model

4.6. Simulating and Modelling ML Algorithms in Weka

Here, we employ the classification algorithms in Weka; cross-validation with ten folds is the test option applied to all techniques. It repeats the entire procedure ten times, calculates the rule using the entire dataset, and outputs the outcome. The ZeroR classifier will not be discussed further because it was chosen as the baseline for the other four classification techniques. Importing the required dataset is the first step in the creation of network intrusion detection models.

4.6.1. Model Built with The Zeror Algorithm (Rules)

The ZeroR classifier just forecasts the predominant category (class). ZeroR does not have prediction power, but it can be used to assess other classification techniques by establishing a baseline performance accuracy. Algorithm. As the genuine baseline, it provides a more trustworthy performance estimate. The true baseline was run using the test option "Use training set" as soon as the UNSW-NB15 dataset had been loaded. This resulted in instances that were correctly classified (119341 - a) at 68.06 percent and instances that were mistakenly classified (56000 - b) at 31.94 percent. This can also be read as 68.06 percent accuracy by class. As illustrated in the diagram below, the confusion matrix, True positive, False positive, Precision, Recall, F-Measure, ROC Area, PRC Area, and Class Rates were all reported.

Figure 8: Performance of ZeroR classifier on UNSW_NB15 dataset

4.6.2. Model Built with The K-Nearest Neighbour Algorithm (Lazy)

In the Weka tool, the KNN method is referred to as IBK, which stands for instance-based. As a result, it is known as the instance-based model, where k is the number of knowledge instances. It constructs the model in 0.03 seconds using the stratified 10-fold cross-validation technique.

KNN had a K value of 3, correctly classifying instances (170114) at 97.02 percent and mistakenly classifying instances (5228) at 2.98 percent. The time required to develop the model grows as the number of k-values climbs as well. More accurately classified instances (accuracy), better Tp, Fp, and Recall results from higher k-values, but lower Precision. According to interpretation, accuracy in each class is 97.02 percent. The table below shows the recorded data for the confusion matrix, True Positive, False Positive, Precision, Recall, F-Measure, MCC, ROC Area, PRC Area, and Class Rates.

Figure 9: Performance of KNN on the UNSW_NB15 dataset

k-value =3

4.6.3. Model Built with The J48 Algorithm (Trees)

The decision tree algorithm took 43.24 seconds to generate the j48 classifier model. It categorised occurrences properly in 173893 cases with a 99.17 percent accuracy rate and inaccurately in 1448 cases with a 0.83 percent accuracy rate. This might also mean that the accuracy for each class is 99.17 percent. As illustrated in the diagram below, the confusion matrix, True positive, False positive, Precision, Recall, F-Measure, ROC Area, PRC Area, and Class Rates were all reported.

Figure 10: Performance of J48 on the UNSW_NB15 dataset

4.6.4. Model Built with The Random Forest Algorithm (Trees)

Building the model for Random Forest bagging in Weka takes 200.24 seconds with 100 iterations and a base learner. 1899 cases were wrongly classified at 1.08 percent, while successfully classified instances (173442) had 98.92 percent. As illustrated in the diagram below, the confusion matrix, True positive, False positive, Precision, Recall, F-Measure, ROC Area, PRC Area, and Class Rates were all reported.

Figure 11: Performance of RF on the UNSW_NB15 dataset

Source: Experimental Analysis 2022

BayesNet using the same stratified cross-validation spent 17.21 seconds in building the model. It has correctly classified instances (168001) at 95.81% and incorrectly classified instances (7340) at 4.19%. This can also be interpreted that accuracy by class is 95.81%. The confusion matrix, True positive, False positive, Precision, Recall, F-Measure, ROC Area, PRC Area, and Class rates were recorded as shown in the diagram below.

4.6.5. Model Built with The Bayes Network Algorithm (Bayes)

Using the same stratified cross-validation, BayesNet built the model in 17.21 seconds. Instances correctly classified (168001) have a 95.81 percent accuracy rate, whereas those mistakenly classified (7340) have a 4.19 percent accuracy rate. This can also be read as 95.81 percent accuracy

by class. As illustrated in the diagram below, the confusion matrix, True positive, False positive, Precision, Recall, F-Measure, ROC Area, PRC Area, and Class Rates were all reported.

Figure 12: Performance of Bayes Net on the UNSW_NB15 dataset

Source: Experimental Analysis 2022

4.7. Estimating The Performance of ML Algorithms in Weka Evaluation Model

Figure 13: Weka-Algorithm-Evaluation-Test-Options

Use training set: It means that the information you studied will be used to test your knowledge. Not widely accepted because you can simply write your code and remember the training examples (which will be in the test).

Supplied test set: You can use this external file as a training set. When you want or need to check the algorithm's knowledge against a particular test set, you can utilize it.

Percentage split: divides the data, designating a certain percentage for learning and the remainder for testing. When your algorithm is sluggish, it is helpful.

Cross-Validation

The preferred approach used for this project is cross-validation. It is a system for determining how a factual dissection will ultimately add up to a separate dataset. It is primarily used in situations where the goal is known, and one wants to make an educated guess about how precisely a prophetic model would function in real-world applications. It is typical to use 10-fold cross-validation. In stratified K-fold cross-validation, the folds are selected so that the mean response value is essentially the same across all of the folds. Cross-validation with 10 folds is the test option that all approaches employ.

In comparison to randomly repeating percentage split evaluations, cross-validation is preferable. The rationale is that each instance is only checked once and appears exactly once in a test set. Repeated random splits are likely to yield less trustworthy results because the variance will be increased while the average will be roughly the same.

4.8. Experimental Results Discussions

Figure 14: Predictive Accuracies of the ML Models

PREDICTIVE ACCURACIES IN BUILDING ML MODELS					
Algorithms	Ac_Training	Ac_Suplied_test	Ac_10-foldCrossV	Ac_5-foldCrossV	Ac_80%SplitTest
Random Forest	100%	55.06%	98.92%	98.86%	98.84%
KNN	98.59%	74.85%	97.00%	96.95%	96.80%
J48	99.72%	53.84%	99.22%	99.15%	99.09%
Bayes Net	95.97%	77.62%	95.81%	95.77%	95.76%
ZeroR	68.06%	55.06%	68.06%	68.06%	68.19%

Source: Experimental Analysis 2022

The table above shows the accuracy results for the training set, supplied test set, 10-fold cross-validation, 5-fold cross-validation, and 80 percent split test sets. Although technically not a component of the models created, ZeroR was simply utilized as a baseline benchmark and has been demonstrated to produce workable results with accuracies above 50%. All algorithms in the training test performed well, which aids in the development of more precise predictive models. To provide a conclusive, objective performance measure of the entire model construction process, the Supplied test set option was also available. Compared to training and other methods, its results were noticeably less impressive, but it nevertheless served its intended role in the model-building process.

Additionally, the 10-fold and 5-fold validation processes were used in the cross-validation process. It is clear from both perspectives that the model produces significantly more accurate results when it is repeated ten times rather than five. Actually, only 10-fold was used in the project; however, 5-fold was added for comparisons solely to drive a point home.

It was also noted that the 80/20 split, which represents the training set and test set, did not perform poorly at all. Only a few decimals separate 10-fold cross-validation from the 80% mark. It was also clear that although the 5-fold cross-validation yielded lesser results than the 10-fold, it still outperformed the 80 percent split.

As a result, it is possible to conclude that the percentage split does not produce as accurate predictive models as the 10-fold cross-validation. As a result, it is frequently used throughout this model building.

Table 4: Correct and Incorrectly Classified Instances

Technique		Results (Accuracy)	
		Correctly Classified Instances	Incorrectly Classified Instances
1.	K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN)	97.02%	2.98%
2.	Random Forest (RF)	98.91%	1.08%
3.	BaiyesNet	95.81%	4.19%
4.	J48	99.17%	0.83%

Source: Experimental Analysis 2022

J48 correctly identified the majority of occurrences, while RF, the KNN, and BayesNet correctly identified the minority. Here, it is concluded that using 10-fold cross-validation, J48 and RF outperformed the other classifiers in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F-measure. However, the sluggish KNN was the fastest in terms of execution time or model building time, clocking in at 0.04 s, while RF was the slowest, taking 200.24 s.

Confusion Matrix

An instrument for visualizing supervised learning is a confusion matrix (in unsupervised learning it is called a matching matrix). An overview of the number of instances a categorization model properly or erroneously predicted.

4.9. Overall Evaluation

According to the analysis of the results in the table below, the network intrusion model with the J48 algorithm outperformed all the other models with a 99.17 percent predictive accuracy, followed by the Random Forest, the KNN algorithm, the BayesNet, and the Logistic Regression with 98.91 percent, 97.02 percent, 95.81 percent, and 93.76 percent, respectively. Another inference that can be made from the findings of the models is that they are suitable for use in any intrusion detection techniques. This is supported by the fact that the True positive, precision recall, f-measure, ROC area, and PRC area all produced good positive results.

Additionally, the MCC's possible values range from -1 to +1. An ideal model has a score of +1, whereas an imperfect model has a score of -1. In addition, when percentages are converted to decimals, all of the MCC values in the table have positive values, which is another argument in favor of calling these models better. One of the main benefits of MCC is its quality because it makes it simple to interpret. Instead, the Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC) is a more dependable statistical measure that only yields a high score if the prediction performed well in each of the four categories of the confusion matrix (true positives, false negatives, true negatives, and false positives), proportionally to the size of the dataset's positive and negative elements.

Another inference from the results is that RF, one of the better at detecting accuracy, takes a long time to create its model, taking 200.24 seconds, whereas KNN generated its model in 0.04 seconds. The least accurate prediction model (BayesNet) ran in 17.21 seconds, whereas J48 executed in a respectable 43.24 seconds.

Figure 15: Performance of the classifiers under cross-validation

Measurements used to Analysed the Outcome										
Algorithms	Accuracy	TP Rate	FP Rate	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	MCC	ROC Area	PRC Area	Execution Time(s)
Random Forest	99%	99%	2%	99%	99%	99%	98%	100%	100%	200.24s
KNN	97%	97%	4%	97%	97%	97%	93%	99%	99%	0.04s
J48	99%	99%	1%	99%	99%	99%	98%	100%	99%	43.24s
Bayes Net	96%	96%	7%	96%	96%	96%	90%	98%	98%	17.21s

The table above made of the 10-fold Cross-Validation

4.10. Comparing Classifiers Using the Weka Experimenter

The Weka ML tool comprises five applications, as was already described earlier, however only the Explorer was used throughout the project to generate models. The inability to make two or more classifiers run simultaneously is one drawback of using the explorer. The use of two datasets simultaneously is also prohibited.

Another program that could be able to fix these explorers' flaws is the Weka Experimenter. While the experimenter can use as many classifiers or datasets as necessary, the explorer is limited to evaluating models separately. In addition to the dataset that was used, the four ML classifiers were therefore loaded into the experimenter in this stage.

Figure 16: Experimenter interface showing the loaded dataset and the four classifiers

The classifiers are loaded, run against the dataset, and then analyzed. Additionally provided below is the performance evaluation table for the classifiers. As with the explorer, there is no need to assess each classifier's performance separately.

Figure 17: The experimenter results evaluation table

Source: Experimental Analysis 2022

The Weka Experimenter allows users to contrast the results of various classifiers on a single or a collection of datasets. According to the aforementioned data, the J48 model had a forecast accuracy of 99.18 percent, followed by RF with 98.89 percent, KNN with 97.02 percent, and BayesNet with a final accuracy of 95.81 percent. The data were evaluated using the 10-fold cross-validation method to test all classifiers.

By choosing either precision, recall, f-measure, or any other evaluation metric under consideration, the Experimenter comparison field allows for the creation of several comparisons. Accuracy (percent correct) was chosen for this project's comparisons, as can be seen above. Also compared were occurrences that were incorrectly classified.

Figure 18: Percentage of incorrectly classified results.

Source: Experimental Analysis 2022

Utilizing the experimenter is intended to produce valid comparisons between the models developed and assessed for this project.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION

5.0. Overview

The network plays a key role in linking the physical and digital worlds. Additionally, several apps that connect to these networks are being created. However, there are risks and threats to the network environment's security due of the open nature of information media and the poor deployment conditions. Among the risks to the network's security are distributed denial of service (DDoS), flooding attacks, man-in-the-middle attacks, denial of service (DoS), wormhole attacks, routing attacks, and hello flood attacks. Therefore, it is necessary to increase the security of the network environment. To stop these attacks and incursions and improve security in these network environments, an intrusion detection system might be developed. This study presents evaluates and discusses models for network intrusion detection. The implementation of the intrusion detection models makes use of supervised machine learning techniques. The J48 Decision Tree, the Random Forest (RF), the Bayesian Network algorithm, and the K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) Classification algorithm are the supervised machine learning approaches used in this paper. In the K-Nearest Neighbor model, different values of K (1 and 3) were tried, and the best results were chosen. Using the UNSW NB15 dataset, the performances of the proposed models were compared to one another. Two distinct sets of the UNSW NB15 dataset were created. Eighty percent of the dataset was used in one set for training, while twenty percent of the dataset was used in the other set for model testing.

The implementation of the models made use of forty-four (44) features from the dataset. The nine categories of network intrusions in the UNSW NB15 dataset are Analysis, Backdoor, DoS, Exploits, Fuzzers, Generic, Reconnaissance, Shellcode, and Worms. The classifiers were trained and tested using the percentage split (80:20), five-fold, and ten-fold cross-validation. The 10-fold

cross-validation produced the model with the highest prediction accuracy, which is why it is preferred in this research. Accuracy, precision, recall, and F-measure were employed as performance indicators for evaluation. The network intrusion detection models were created using the Weka Machine Learning workbench. A company can genuinely achieve its full potential with the aid of weka data mining. It is a means to evaluate the effects that particular traits are having on a company and could aid business owners in increasing profits and averting mistakes in the future. In essence, a company employs this technique to look at specific data from several perspectives to get a whole picture of how its operations are developing. Owners of businesses can obtain a thorough understanding of topics including client trends, prospective income leakage, and potential money makers. The information might also highlight methods for a business to cut wasteful expenses and perhaps boost overall revenue.

According to the findings obtained, J48 performed the best and had an average execution time. The execution time for RF was the longest. KNN's execution time was the quickest, and its performance results were marginally worse than those of J48 and RF. In conclusion, J48 offers the optimum balance between execution speed and performance.

5.1. Research Limitations

The project has limitations, even though this study presented and examined network intrusion detection models utilizing machine learning techniques such as KNN, J48, RF, and BayesNet. Based on research done by Kumar et al., (2020) features in the UNSW NB15 dataset were chosen. Without examining how the chosen features may impact the developed models' accuracy of detection and recall, they were used. Since smaller datasets are simpler to analyze, feature reduction poses a compromise between accuracy and simplicity, the research used relatively little feature selection (dimensionality reduction).

5.2.Future Works

Future studies may expand the model construction to take into account additional techniques like neural networks and support vector machines. With the UNSW-NB15 dataset, unsupervised ML methods can also be used. WEKA enables the implementation of supervised and unsupervised classifiers built-in Python (ScikitLearnClassifier), allowing for the comparison of findings with those from this research study. Additionally, a distinct dataset can be utilized to train and test the models, ensuring that they can recognize intrusions.

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